

Game, Set and Attune

A Political Attunement Model for
Limiting Extreme Narratives and
Building Democratic Capacity

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A Political Attunement Model for Limiting Extreme Narratives and Building Democratic Capacity

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1. Introduction				
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1.2. Existing Attunement studies and interventions		✓	✓	
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2.1. How does political attunement relate to harmony?	✓	✓	✓	
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3. The Political Attunement Model				
3.1. Using a tennis metaphor – political attunement and political gameplaying	✓	✓	✓	✓
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4. Discussions – Assumptions within the Attunement Model		✓	✓	
5. Conclusion	✓	✓	✓	

Executive Summary

- Attunement is a process which has been developed across a number of disciplines in terms of affective attunement, preconscious attunement, self-other intersubjective attunement and the interpretative attunement associated with cultural studies. In the OppAttune project the focus is specifically on **political attunement**.
- Political Attunement is defined here as a dynamic relational interaction between oppositional entities, whether individuals, groups, parties or nations. Political Attunement involves positional play whilst acknowledging the political legitimacy and rights of the other party.
- This model uses the metaphor of a tennis game, to enable the necessary translation of political attunement to different target audiences, national contexts and political events. Building on evidence which shows that citizens understand political decision-making through metaphorical reasoning.
- Political Attunement is a process which promotes sustained dialogue or exchange between oppositional parties whether individual citizens, groups, parties or other entities (referred to as parties in this report). Political attunement aims to limit everyday extremism and its potential escalation. It also aims to build democratic capacity within Europe, across its citizens, communities and nation-states (as related to the European Democratic Action Plan).
- A key parameter of attunement is that it assumes that the two parties have oppositional rights claims, worldviews, identifications and goals. In attempting to achieve political goals or legitimate claims the two parties could adopt politically extreme narratives and engage in what OppAttune terms everyday extremism. Political Attunement assumed everyday extremism has the potential, through the adoption of extreme narratives, to lead into hostile and violent political extremism.
- Equally the move to adopting increasingly extreme political narratives, can be related to a lack of democratic capacity-building, in young people, or a failure to develop democratic capacity, in groups, communities and national discourse.
- Parameters - Attempts at consensus building or reconciliation are not political attunement. Rather attunement is a process of acknowledging the validity of the other, and staying in engagement with their positions, worldviews, identification, underlying beliefs.
- This attunement model has been developed in collaboration with partners across the entire consortium. As such it is a transdisciplinary model drawing on psychology, anthropology, sociology, political science, economics as well as philosophy and history.
- The political attunement model was developed in dialogue with partners within the two sibling projects SMIDGE and ARENAS, and supports the overall aim articulated by the European Commission of understanding and limiting the evolution of extreme political narratives.
- The OppAttune project provides practitioners, policy-makers and scientists a set of attunement tools to tackle the rise of political extremism and build democratic capacity.

Using the Attunement Model

- The political attunement model requires three steps, 1) deciding on the everyday extremism scenario, 2) agreeing what constitutes success and valid measures of everyday extremism as related to context and finally, 3) selecting the attunement tool.
- There are four key types of attunement tools: Rights & Regulations Attunement Tools, Limiting Mobilisation Attunement Tools, Living Democracy Attunement Tools & Public Dialogue Attunement Tools (see Appendix A for user-guides).
- The Attunement User Guides in Appendix A form the basis of the interventions carried out within WP7 alongside Deliverable 7.1 together these tools, models and guidance aim to limit everyday extremism and build democratic capacity.

Parameters of the Attunement Model

- A risk of the attunement model is that it reflects the positional limitations of the practitioner using it. Political attunement and the use of attunement tools require a clear scenario where everyday extremism is rising, so that a pre- and post-event approach can ideally be used.
- Using political attunement should not be regarded as a replacement for attempts at coalition or consensus-building. The model works with an assumption of oppositional worldviews, and dissensus and its tools are designed for vexed situations which have been evidenced as related to polarisation and everyday extremism.

1

Introduction: Towards Political Attunement

Over the last decade, there has been a substantial rise in extreme political narratives which are contributing to polarisation (Garzia, Da Silva, and Maye, 2023; Schmidt-Catran and Czymara, 2023). Such extreme narratives diminish both an individual and collective democratic capacity as well undermines citizens political literacy. This rise in extremism relates to divisive narratives which promote binary ‘us vs them’ logics and worldviews in which every political challenge risks becoming a zero-sum game. This binary is further supported by partisan media ecosystems transform disinformation into ‘fact’, increasing exclusive trust and introducing a sense of time-urgency (BBC Morning Live Film, Mahendran & English, 2025). This inability to seek collaboration based on factual reality for challenging political issues (be that the climate crisis, increasing income inequalities, or similar global issues) threatens not only the European Union Project, but citizens’ beliefs in representational democratic processes or even the concept of democracy itself.

Politics in most nation-states is arranged along partisan oppositional lines, though newer parliaments have established hemicycle structures to promote all party working or cross-party working (e.g. European Parliament, Germany, Scotland), generally politics is structured as an oppositional process. A core tenet of the OppAttune project and its consortium of partners is that healthy democracies require individuals to be political in oppositional environments and develop the ability to understand and reject extreme narratives which hinge on divisive binaries. This naturally leads to a tension between managing oppositional contexts, whilst not moving too far towards extremism. The OppAttune project and its 17-partner consortium was established to build democratic resilience and capacity in the face of growing political extreme narratives.

The OppAttune project responds to this threat to democracy by focusing on three objectives.

Track

the evolution of extreme political narratives within media, local ecologies and living democracies and establish the psychological, sociological and anthropological drivers of extremism.

Attune

capacity for public dialogue by modelling how the evolution of extreme political narratives impacts on social and political dialogue.

Limit

the rise of extreme political narratives and their potential to become violent political transformations disrupting democratic processes such as democratic elections.

Delivering on these objectives will contribute towards the key challenge of strengthening democratic resilience, as highlighted in the European Democratic Action Plan and OppAttune contributed to the recent Democratic Shield consultation. The ability to navigate oppositional tension, where there are differences in worldviews, life experiences and aspiration, is often understood in terms of democratic deliberation or the development

panels. Central to the approach taken here is to propose a process of political attunement, which enables citizens who face each other to navigate their desire to “win”, through positional play, strategies and tactics whilst remaining within the rule of law. This report sets out the theoretical basis to the Political Attunement Model, then the key questions that guide the use of the model and in the final section it presents the tool-kits which were developed for partners to test the model in a variety of situations, events and national contexts.

The multi-level model presented in this report has been designed for six different target groups across a variety of different cultural and political contexts. The use of the political attunement model and the range of attunement tools, will through its implementation and testing in the final phase of OppAttune offer decision-makers, practitioners and the general public an opportunity to develop a sense of the attunement process and its validity for navigating vexed political issues where consensus may not be possible or desirable. It has been developed into a user-friendly interactive which enables the general public to engage in assessing their own attunement and democratic style (Deliverable D6.7), it will also be presented directly to practitioners, media and national and European policymakers at the OppAttune Winter Academy, Coimbra, Portugal 26–28th November 2025.

Target Groups using Political Attunement

General
Public

Media
Influencers

Political
Actors

Practitioners &
Policymakers

Research
Community

Young
Citizens

The specific focus of the Political Attunement Model is on how democratic practices are enacted in a person’s everyday life, such as posting political content on social media or political activism in their local community, in order to understand how actions and narratives that threaten democracy emerge from everyday acts. These everyday acts are understood within the OppAttune project as **Everyday Extremism**. This concept is being developed within the consortium across a transdisciplinary team. Although the concept will be discussed later in the report, in brief, everyday extremism refers to two processes: firstly, the process by which extreme narratives become mainstreamed and normalised within everyday political discourse (be that online or in-person) through words and/or images, and secondly when individuals begin to act in extreme ways in a routine or quotidian manner, often unaware that their prosaic actions are extreme.

Everyday Extremism can lead to dehumanisation, and within this model an extreme narrative is something that can be understood as oppressive or symbolically violent, which indicate hostility towards another individual, entity or group. It can develop into an active process of limiting this person, entity or group’s ability to engage in democracy. The process of political attunement rests on the proposal that everyone has the capacity to engage in everyday extremism on-line and in certain situations when they become engaged in a vexed social or political issue. Everyday Extremism is something that has the potential to escalate into something more harmful if it is not limited by democratic nations, who value liberal freedoms but equally wish to balance such freedoms within a regulatory framework.

1.1 Working Definition

Political Attunement therefore involves anticipating and acknowledging the other as an oppositional player. It involves an on-going process of dynamic relational interaction between oppositional entities, whether individuals, groups, parties or nations.

Critically it requires positional and relational play whilst acknowledging the political legitimacy and rights of the other person or party. We propose that Political Attunement has the potential to reduce the rise of everyday extremism, in two ways. Firstly, it reduces de-humanisation and the normalisation of extreme narratives and second it builds democratic capacity to take up a number of flexible positions, rather than act from within rigid identity in-group loyalties. to sustain dialogue. This occurs in a dynamic process of new positions, accords, discords and the development of emerging shared political narratives about democracy itself.

Figure 1. Initial Visual Representation of the Attunement Model (Grant Agreement No. Horizon-Europe: 101095170, UKRI: 10071909)

Political attunement when it is functioning effectively allows active citizens on-line and off-line to acknowledge partisan differences, counteract attempts at divisive mobilisation whilst equally resisting calls for coalitions and consensus-building. In this respect this is a relationship between political attunement and existing models of agnostic democracy (Mouffe, 2013). It could be assumed then that political attunement relates to individual or interpersonal skills development. However, in our initial working articulation of the proposed attunement model (Figure 1), we were clear that this model would need to include rule of law, freedom of speech, psychological drivers, as well as deeply rooted sociological and anthropological sense-making. Figure 1, shows how it was initially presented in the proposal in response to the European Commission's call to understand the *evolution of political extremism and its influence on contemporary social and political dialogue*. In the next section, the theoretical basis of political attunement is discussed.

Political Attunement

Political Attunement can be understood as a dynamic relational interaction between oppositional entities, whether individuals, groups, parties or nations. Critically it involves positional play whilst acknowledging the political legitimacy and rights of the other party. Political Attunement reduces everyday extremism, in two ways it reduces de-humanisation and the normalisation of extreme narratives, and it also builds democratic capacity to take up several positions, to sustain dialogue, in terms of new positions, accords, discords and the development of emerging shared political narratives. Whilst equally acknowledging partisan differences and resisting calls for consensus-building.

1.2 Existing Attunement Studies and Interventions

The process of attunement can be traced back to the philosophies of Johann Gottfried von Herder (1744–1803) and Immanuel Kant (1724–1804). Specifically, attunement was discussed within the context of German aesthetic theory and its focus on relationships to beauty. For Kant, attunement is

an interaction between understanding and imagination, i.e.: between the law-based rigidity of understanding and the unanchored freedoms of imagination (Lozar, 2009; Zigon, 2014). Brigstocke and Noorani (2016) argue that there are four scholarly traditions which attempt to define attunement at this phenomenological level. Phenomenology being the philosophy of experience (i.e.: how humans experience phenomena and its impact on subjective experiences). We discuss these traditions below.

1.3 Four Traditions of Attunement

The first tradition relates to *Understanding & Imagination*, as previously mentioned Kantian focus on the interplay between understanding and imagination. In terms of human interactions, Kant's idea of attunement is one in which a reflective self-awareness (*Sensus Communis*) creates a capacity for empathising with their possible feelings and judgements (Jackson, 2016). *Preconscious Attunement* – the second tradition – considers a person's preconscious capacity for attuning themselves to their environment; specifically, the uncontrollable capacities for awareness, passivity and receptivity that influence moments of attunement. *Empathetic Interactions* – the third line of inquiry within the existing literature – is focused on a more explicitly psychological tradition. Attunement as an affective process, where attunement is considered akin to empathic responses between two individuals. That is to say, the manifestation of an internal affective state into real-world interactions which can influence subsequent events and development. Frequently the dyadic focus is on the affective attunement between a parent/guardian and a child in their care (Miller et al, 2018). For example, in developmental psychology a key part of the attunement process examines focus on non-verbal communication between two or more persons and how they can dynamically align in such a context (Hart, 2016). A key feature of this is the process of Affective Attunement – the ability to understand and attune to what another person may be feeling without verbal communication. This is typically explored in the context of early infancy interactions between the child and the parent or primary caregiver (Bentzen & Hart, 2015; Khakhalova, 2021; Legerstee, Markova, and Fisher, 2007).

It is worth noting, particularly for further development of attunement processes, that healthcare and mental wellbeing are two other areas in which the process of attunement is currently being used. It is used to consider non-verbal communication dynamic between caregivers and patients with dementia (Van Der Geugten and Goossensen, 2020). A meta-ethnographic review of communication dynamic between caregiver and patient found attunement to be a dynamic process in which both parties reach out to communicate. The caregiver instinctively interprets the non-verbal communication signals from the patient and aligns their actions with the person accordingly (Krøier, McDermott, and Ridder 2022).

In the final tradition, attunement relates to *Past & Future Relations of the self*, this approach understands the process of attunement in terms of transcending the immediate temporal and spatial realms to explore how individuals relate and attune to past and future versions of the self. Attunement is also considered to play an essential role in psychotherapy (Talia, et al. 2018). In a clinical context, the concept of attunement attempts to elucidate individuals share emotional states when interacting with others (Briggs, 2015; Holck & Geretsegger, 2016). Specifically, the idea of *Emotional Attunement* and how developing the ability to attune to how others feel allows one the opportunity to foster stronger interpersonal or work relationships (Forlè, 2024). Regardless of the academic discipline, the concept of attunement in all cases focuses on the dynamic process in which individuals align themselves to an external stimulus to achieve a harmonious relationship.

Unsurprisingly, attunement also features in studies within the arts on the role music performs in mood regulation for the user (i.e.: the various 'listening modes' in which a person interacts with music – listening for pleasure, emotional catharsis, background noise, etc.) (Reybrouck, 2023; Volgsten, 2019). The concept of attunement is used as a metaphor by Tina M. Campt to suggest how one can understand

photography depicting black subjects (specifically, the suggestion that attuning to the ‘frequency’ of the image affords a window into the agitative spaces of black subjects in otherwise violent images (Normann, 2019).

The concept of intersubjective attunement, as developed by the social psychologist Ragnar Rommetveit, is core to the form of attunement developed here (Rommetveit, 1998; Linnell, 2017). Rommetveit was concerned with attunement in the context of language, meaning and dialogue where there may well be power asymmetries. This form of intersubjective attunement requires a form of working order. As Duranti and Mattina who have developed a contemporary account of cooperation, explain:

“To introduce the notion of attunement, one must first realize that, as conversation analysts have shown, even the acts of speaking that appear to be the most ritualized and routine, such as starting a telephone conversation cannot simply be taken for granted because each act of speaking involves negotiations and cooperation toward a working order” (Duranti & La Mattina, 2022 p.90)

Rommetveit proposes that we attune to the attunement of the other in the sense that we try to anticipate how others will regard our own views. In more conflictual encounters, this can be in the form of disputational, exploratory and cumulative dialogue as it occurs in learning settings (Wegerif & Mercer, 1997) but for our purposes here the future-orientation central to Lisa Blackman’s use of attunement begins to articulate its potential for political dialogue. Blackman – inspired in part by the attunement shown when partners dance together – adapts this to the processes of becoming political, where “Attunement points towards modes of communication that trouble separation, boundedness and singularity, and which reveal how bodies (human and non-human) are always in a process of becoming” (Blackman p.138). This more political attunement sees multiplicities as a political act and is centred on a politics of hope in relation to democracies-yet-to-come. It is precisely this future-orientation, that informs the development of the political attunement model below, which enables oppositional partners within an attunement game to anticipate the attunement of the other, but equally not succumb to oppositional hostilities (Andreouli, et al, 2025). In other words, to enable citizens’ abilities to be political within divisive times without turning hostile (Mahendran, Obradovic, Nieland, & Weinberg, 2024).

Political Attunement and its Parameters

2.1 How does political attunement relate to harmony?

Many of the existing theories, studies and interventions aimed at addressing declining democratic capacities and rising hostilities focus on harmony, particularly within the Social Sciences, Humanities & Arts (SHAPE) disciplines. Focusing on harmony could be relevant in a political context if process-orientated – i.e. it is applied to attempt to understand how the public engage during interactions over vexed polarising issues. However, if harmony is seen as a key outcome (i.e.: a shorthand for consensus) this risks limiting democratic capacity within the political attunement model, because of the need, as we argue above, for dissensus within democratic processes. A key assumption here is that implementing tools which allow an individual or group to engage in oppositional thinking without resorting to polarising dehumanisation offers a critical form of democracy, which anticipates radicalisation, and everyday extremism rather than appeals to common-in-group processes and striving towards transitory moments of consensus (Mahendran & English, 2021; Obradovic & English, 2024).

2.2 How does political attunement relate to consensus-building?

The dominant approach to the public being political relates to building consensus and cohesion. Influencing this could be the focus on the idea of consensus within the political domain. A result orientated approach which prioritises agreement (no matter how tenuous) over the potential for meaningful disagreement which, potentially, has a value to society. The core tenet of the OppAttune project which underpins the concept of political attunement is that consensus is not always realistic when considering power asymmetries, the polarising impact of politics and competing rights and aims. This occurs within the context of what are understood as cultural differences (culture wars) where one worldview is seen as a symbolic threat to another worldview to such an extent that there is no comfortable middle-ground for parties to position themselves. Indeed, it could be argued that consensus is neither achievable nor even desirable as an outcome given that an overemphasis on consensus, could limit the public's capacity for democratic engagement (e.g.: the right to peaceful protest.). In such circumstances, rather than seeking to create a consensus, the OppAttune project argues that understanding the macro, meso, and micro levels factors can create the environment for attunement and offer a route to limiting the evolution of extreme narratives and building democratic capacities and democratic public spheres.

2.3 How does attunement relate to social cohesion?

Although attunement implies a relational dynamic between two entities in direct confrontation so that they may recognise the legitimacy of those with opposing views, attunement is not limited in this regard. Indeed, it could take many forms; be that individuals using attunement toolkits to navigate their rights in difficult circumstances or young citizens developing skills in which they attune themselves to identify fact-based news in a world of online disinformation. Previous European Commission funded projects offer insights into how creating a collaborative environment and applying the relevant interventionist tools can foster an understanding on the dynamics of social cohesion. The D.Rad project (De-Radicalisation in Europe and Beyond: Detect, Resolve, Reintegrate), which ran from December 2020 to April 2024, brought together 17 partners across Europe and the Middle East to examine the drivers of radicalisation and polarisation, particularly among young people in urban and peri-urban areas. D.Rad’s conceptual framework is the I-GAP spectrum, which identifies four interlinked stages leading to radicalisation: (1) Injustice: Perceptions of systemic discrimination, (2) Grievance: Emotional responses to this perceived discrimination, (3) Alienation: Disconnection from wider society, and (4) Polarisation: Deepening divisions that can lead to extremist beliefs and/or actions. The project aims focused on three core elements: (1) Detect Trends: Identify actors, networks, and contexts driving radicalisation in everyday settings, (2) Resolve Drivers: Understand how grievances and alienation transform into radicalisation, both online and offline, and (3) Reintegration and Inclusion: Develop strategies to reintegrate individuals affected by radicalisation without compromising liberties. Outputs from D.RAD offers salient insights on social cohesion that are relevant to OppAttune’s aims to attune those engaged in everyday extremism.

D.RAD’s findings indicate that the erosion of social cohesion emerges from daily experiences of injustice in online spaces (as opposed to a single exposure to an extremist ideology). This supports the attunement assumptions of OppAttune that there is greater overall benefit in developing tools that tackle daily hostile encounters which could lead ‘everyday extremism’ among the general public, as opposed to focusing on infrequent occurrences of the type of radicalization which leads to violence. Moreover, D.RAD’s finding that online platforms can amplify feelings of grievance and facilitate the spread of polarising narratives is also highly salient to processes of political attunement. Moreover, D.RAD’s understanding that civic education can serve as a key preventive measure towards maintaining social cohesion offers a foundational premise for WP5’s attunement tool ‘Polarisation Us & Them – Understanding Vertical & Horizontal Populism Tool’, which aims to educate the public as to the dynamics of populism on everyday political encounters as well as WP4’s insights into how far-right extreme narratives are mainstreamed via the sharing of memes and how it’s normalisation impacts on social cohesion (Askanius & Stoencheva, 2024).

Another Horizon-funded project, VOLPOWER, focused on how volunteering in sports can be harnessed as a tool for social cohesion and integration. The project focused on understanding and

fostering social cohesion and integration between EU nationals and third-country nationals (TCNs) aged 18–27 to explore the challenges the latter face when settling into a new community. The project’s key findings offer insights into the value of this type of volunteering in creating social cohesion among this target group. VOLPOWER found that participation in volunteering activities (especially sports and arts) significantly enhanced intercultural understanding and reduced perceived social distance between EU and TCN youth. The project found that volunteering in mixed-gender and inter-cultural settings increased each volunteers’ potential for bridging social capital, highlighting the potential for longer-term social cohesion among the cohort. The experience of volunteering also offered participants an opportunity for self-reflection to identify areas for skill development regarding how they engage with those from different cultural backgrounds. Whilst the context is different to OppAttune, this focus on youth engagement with different cultural perspectives and worldviews is highly salient to WP 5’s attunement interventions (see Attunement Tool – Narrative Group Work). For example, the work package’s focus on narrative group work among young people supports VOLPOWER’S finding that the type of activities which foreground valuing working as a collective can foster a greater social cohesion. Moreover, WP5’s ethnographically focused trust-building games aligns with the importance of allowing for dissensus whilst balancing this against the “rules of the game” towards some degree of social cohesion, which goes beyond Mouffe’s emphasis on agonism towards the idea of attuned oppositional dialogue and political behaviours.

2.4 How does political attunement relate to radicalisation?

OppAttune priorities relate to everyday extremism with two specific aims, to build democratic capacity to be political, and equally to limit everyday extremism, so that it does not escalate into violent extremism. To support this, this final section considers the relationship between political attunement and radicalisation further. There are several models which attempt to explain radicalisation within the context of terrorism. For example, Borum’s Four-Stage Model of the Terrorist Mindset, Moghaddam’s Staircase to Terrorism or Precht’s Model of a “Typical” Radicalization Pattern. Nehlsen et al (2020) discuss evaluation research on violent extremism using the Logic Model. This is a graphical depiction of the rationale and expectations of a program and how it aligns with their overall aims. In this respect it does not articulate any insights into the process of how extremist views develop and manifest. A frequently cited model (Figure 2) is Canetti-Nisim, Halperin, Sharvit, Hobfoll’s (2009) *Stress-Based Model of Political Extremism*. This cognitive-focused model attempts to predict political extremism via assessing an individual’s psychological distress in the context of threat exposure to terrorist acts (see image below). A limitation with this model is that it does not place much value on the temporal dynamics of political extremism. Specifically, the likelihood that long-term exposure to extreme narratives, which are then re-enforced in real-world and on-line settings, are potentially more important than short-term effects of psychological distress to a terrorist attack in which the person was not directly involved (Borum, 2011).

Figure 2. Stress based model of political extremism
Reference Source: (Canetti-Nisim, Halperin, Sharvit, and Hobfoll, 2009).

Arguably, a more relevant model for a model of political attunement is the one developed by Rothut et al (2024) as it focuses on extremism rather than terrorism and how such ideas are mainstreamed into familiar political narratives. The authors argue that, due to the long-term and gradual nature of this *mainstreaming* of extreme narratives, the process presents a challenge for researchers to operationalise and understand. Based on a systematic review, two communicative steps are proposed (1) Content positioning (the insertion ideas into the mainstream) and (2) Susceptibility (speaking to the specific concerns of sections of the public), alongside the 12 contributing factors that must be presenting for this mainstreaming process (see Figure 3; Rothut et al (2024). For content positioning, the contributing factors are (1) Undermining popular discourses (e.g.: hijacking hashtags). (2) Dog whistling, (3) Calculated provocation, (4) Social media exploitation (co-ordinated attacks), Hyper partisanship, and (6) Issue poisoning in mainstream news outlets. For susceptibility, the contributing factors are: (7) Humours communication, (8) Visual elements, (9) Targeted appeals, (10) Democratically elected actors (act as ‘boosters’), (11) Populist out-group attacks, and (12) Victimisation. This idea of ‘susceptibility’ aligns with WP 6’s WiDE Lens Survey and its focus on the drivers that, be they worldviews, identifications and/or disaffections, that increase the likelihood of endorsing everyday extremism. Aspects of the content positioning communication also align with OppAttune’s research aimed to develop attunement tools. Namely, WP 6’s Four Nation Pairing Study which explores how individuals engage in direct conversation on the polarising issue of immigration. Especially how paired individuals engage in hyper partisanship, active provocation, and use humour in the discursive space to disrupt factual exchanges in the hope of ‘winning’ the dispute. However, a limitation with the model is one the authors themselves acknowledge, i.e.: the systematic literature review on which the model is based does not include any theoretical content (i.e.: the focus is on

outcomes). Therefore, whilst it may offer insight into incidents of mainstreaming, the review lacks any theoretical underpinning from which to understand the processes at work.

Figure 3. Conceptualization of mainstreaming
Reference Source: Rothut, Schulze, Rieger, and Naderer (2024)

In this regard existing literature does not offer, as yet, sufficient insights into a public which may engage in more pervasive forms of Everyday Extremism. That said, current Horizon-Europe projects SMIDGE (*Social Media Narratives: Addressing Extremism in Middle Age*) has deliverables which offer content that is highly salient to OppAttune's aims to track, attune, and limit the spread of everyday extremism. For example, SMIDGE have developed an extremism database, online platform cataloguing extremist narratives across major social media platforms. The database categorizes content promoting far-right, religious, anti-vaccine, and conspiracy narratives, which offers researchers and policymakers with data to inform evidence-based decisions. This database offers OppAttune a complimentary data source to contextualise WP6's WiDE Lens survey findings on the drivers of extremism by offering an understanding into where this polarising content emerges in the digital sphere. The conceptualisation within the Smidge Project understood as Hybridized Prefatory Extremism (HYPE) also compliments the attunement work in WP4 in how it describes the blending of extremist content with mainstream media, often through humour and ambiguous displays of ideology. Here HYPE provides an understanding of how nuanced and sophisticated this type of content can be and, therefore, offers a steer towards what OppAttune tools can be best implemented in attempting to attune and limit the spread of extremism.

ARENAS (*Analysis of and Responses to Extremist Narratives*) is a Horizon Europe-funded initiative focused on understanding and countering extremist narratives that influence political and social life in Europe. The project examines how these narratives impact discourses related to science, gender, and the nation, aiming to empower individuals to resist them and promote harmonious living across Europe. Whilst all of ARENAS' objectives have relevance to the broad aims of understanding political extremism, two of the five objectives especially resonant with OppAttune's aims. Specific objective 1 (Identify, Analyse, and Characterise Extremist Narratives) offers a comparative context when considering the parameters of the OppAttune-developed concept of everyday extremism (i.e.: how does a comparable project define political extremism? Do these definitions offer potential ontological conflicts and, if so, what are the implications for OppAttune's concepts and aims?). Specific objective 3's (Explain the Influence on Perceptions and Actions) analysis of how extremist narratives spread among young people compliments OppAttune's focus on understanding how the youth engage with political extremism. Specifically, the joint aim of both projects to develop culturally relevant education materials that stakeholders can implement long after the project has concluded. Whilst neither project focuses specifically on the concept of everyday extremism, the broader aims and outputs from both offers OppAttune with a valuable context in which to contextualise and evaluate our own progress.

3

The Political Attunement Model

OppAttune’s aim to track, attune and limit the spread of everyday extremism centres on adapting the concepts articulated above into a working model to be tested by partners in their interventions. This model and its user-guides, provides a variety of stakeholders with attunement tools that can be applied to limit everyday extremism in an actionable and measurable manner. Therefore, there is value in considering how previous Horizon-Europe funded projects have produced and presented models which aim to inform on the features of political extremism. The VOX-POL: Virtual Center of Excellence for Research in Violent Online Political Extremism, a project which ran from Jan 2014 to Dec 2019, and aimed to improve the understanding of violent online political extremism and terrorism. Specifically, the role of digital technologies, especially AI, in spreading extremist material and to create training, resources, and tools to support counter-extremism measures for policymakers and practitioners. The Affordance Map of AI (Figure 4) categorises AI technologies into three primary models and how they facilitate the spread of extremist content. The first is Generative Models (i.e.: large language models and deepfake technologies that create text, images, etc.) which can be used by extremists to produce fake content (impersonate individuals, etc.) or dehumanising propaganda. Secondly there are Pattern-Recognition Model which can be repurposed by extreme political actors for surveillance and targeting by identifying patterns in data. The third component is the Decision-Making Models, which enable extremists to plan and implement their attack plan. This Affordance Map of AI offers the OppAttune project valuable insights into how AI technologies can spread extreme narratives in digital spaces which is relevant to the research focus of WP4 (Media, Machines & Mobilisation). The model also offers the potential to compare the process of initial creation between memes with explicitly violent content (shared by a minority) and the symbolic violence of everyday extremism memes. Therefore, offering a valuable comparative context for identifying the ‘markers’ of everyday extremism in the digital sphere and how it differs in the developmental phase and the implications for the political attunement tools that OppAttune has developed.

Figure 4. Affordance Map of AI Extremism
Reference Source: Baele and Brace (2019).

Another Horizon-Europe funded project which has produced a useful model for OppAttune's attunement aims is PRIME (Preventing, Interdicting and Mitigating Extremist events: Defending against lone actor extremism) which ran from May 2014 to April 2017. PRIME's key aim was to develop strategies that can mitigate or prevent lone actor extremist events (i.e.: terrorist acts in which an individual acted alone) as they are notoriously difficult to detect. To counter this, PRIME developed the PRIME's Risk Analysis Framework (RAF) offers a multi-level framework to identify and analyse risk factors associated with lone actor extremist events. In terms of its key focus, PRIME is the anthesis of OppAttune's interest in everyday extremism that can be enacted by most people (as opposed to violent political extremism enacted by one person). However, the multi-level focus on individual, situational, social, and systemic is salient to OppAttune's interest in exploring macro-, meso- and micro-level factors which influence everyday extremism. In this regard, the RAF offers a template for understanding how a model can be devised and disseminated to offer insight at these different levels in a way which is relevant to the intended stakeholders.

As outlined in the introduction, OppAttune aims to track the evolution of everyday political extremism and test a series of interventions at the national and transnational levels which may limit the spread of extreme dialogue. Rather than focusing on extremism which engages in hate speech or incites violence, the aim is to understand and limit the spread of extreme narratives which occur during seemingly 'common sense' discussions about polarising issues – i.e.: 'everyday extremism'. This could be a thoughtless social media post or share which contains extreme content or an extremist opinion voiced in our daily interactions with those around us. These are narratives that occur in everyday speech and interactions that stop short of outright hostility. Such an action would be considered 'everyday extremism' due to the harm it may cause in the first instance and its potential for escalation if encouraged. A key assumption here is that everyone has the capacity to engage in everyday extremism.

3.1 Attunement and Political Game-Playing

Within the attunement model we use a tennis game metaphor. Metaphorical reasoning has been shown to be involved in political judgement from the figurations proposed by Rosie Braidotti, in the context of migration and European Citizenship, natural disaster metaphors to describe immigrants and the management of immigration (Goodman & Kirkwood, 2019), the queue jumping metaphor used by sociologist Arlie Hochschild, in her ethnographic exploration of the American Tea Party, to empirical studies by political psychologists which showed metaphorical reasoning is central to political reasoning (Bougher, 2012) and persuasion (Landau & Keefer, 2015).

Using a tennis metaphor, whether lawn tennis, wheel-tennis, or table tennis, connects to the on-going articulation of politics as a form of game playing, which whilst in the short-term of the game, creates scenarios of winners and losers. Over the longer-term involves acknowledging the rule of law and accepting that you will be able to play again. However, there are risks in this, in both trivialising the high stakes of political interest and how they shape citizens lives, in terms of over-emphasizing adversarial tactics against cooperation in what could be judged a zero-sum game. These risks were discussed in two consortium meetings with the full OppAttune consortium, and the use of the tennis metaphor did not reach consensus, with certain work package teams preferring the term social resonance or preferring to site the processes of attunement within a more communal and less dyadic space. It seems that tennis players themselves tend to emphasize that the game is competitive, but it also requires compassion (see Mariah Burton Nelson, Embracing Victory for a tennis player’s exploration of this).

The authors of this report make the case therefore that the tennis metaphor – whether court tennis, lawn tennis, wheel or table tennis – has the advantages in having agreed rules of the game, the presence of the crowd, and coaches. It also critically, allows players to know they will be able to play again, even if they lose this time (a kin to elections). In this regard, the tennis match is less normative than other dynamic relational spaces – even if it inevitably dyadic between two or four players.

- (A) Ground (determines lines) = WP5
- (B) Lines. Net & Umpire (rule enforcement) = WP2
- (C) Players (actors interacting - people, nations) = WP6
- (D) Coaches (protect & attack encouragement) = WP3
- (E) Crowd (influences players) = WP4

Figure 5. Attunement Model – Tennis Metaphor

3.2 Game, Set, Attune – Political Attunement and the tennis metaphor

Positional responses, acknowledging the other, resisting mobilisation from the crowd, being buoyed by the crowd, tactical and strategic decision and continual rallying are all features of tennis, which can be related to specific processes of political attunement. Political attunement is necessarily a multi-level process, which relates to the crowd’s ability to withstand disinformation, resistance mobilisation, how to access the rules, accepting that the ball is out, as well as the right to appeal. Whereas the umpire can be related to rights and regulations (specifically findings from OppAttune’s WP2 and its deliverables), the influenced of the crowd can relate to findings from WP4. The extent to which the ground may be influenced and not a “level-playing field” relates to the deliverables presented by WP5. We propose the on-going existence of coaching is potentially informed from findings arising from WP3. Finally, the psychological drivers of each player particularly their positional flexibility, capacities and orientations can be related to the findings arising out of WP6. See Section 3.3, for a fuller account of how the political attunement model is built from the findings arising from OppAttune’s transdisciplinary work packages 2–6.

It is important, if political attunement is to build democratic capacity, that the purpose of its application is to ensure citizens want to play the game rather than focus only on winning the game. This means that the application of the attunement model fosters a desire to do politics and be political (Mahendran, Obradovic, Nieland & Weinber, 2024), a commitment to maintain the rules of the political game involving both acknowledging and understanding the legitimacy of the other player, and also understanding one’s own playing and the potential problems with that e.g. knee-jerk reaction, intolerance, de-humanisation etc. in order to develop democratic resilience.

In developing this model, a key question to consider at this point is what would be considered attunement (see figure 6)? What would a successful political attunement entail and how is it to be defined? As outlined in the opening section, European politics and beyond are experiencing an especially polarising and turbulent period in which the ability to engage with those that have differing political agendas (be that as individuals, groups or nations) is extremely limited. In such circumstances, an intervention which affords the relevant target group the tools to create a space in which to engage and acknowledge the other despite political diffe-

rences would be an initial success. To keep with the tennis metaphor, in today's political climate, players all too frequently exist in this polarising state about the game and do not wish to play a rally. It could be that they suspect the umpire to be part of a conspiracy against them (how regulatory rights influence extremism – WP2) or are overly concerned with disinformation shouted from the crowd (the influence of online extremist narratives – WP4). Perhaps they view the ground '*as not a level playing field*' or mistrust that the ground will be suited to their style of play (the anthropological drivers that influence limitation perceptions – WP5). Players could approach the game in an overly defensive and aggressive way as a consequence of their coaches, which we relate to the role of protectionist decision-making, on-shoring decisions, on behavioural biases drawing on WP3. Such influences may create a context in which the players are 'de-attuned' to what is required of them to productively function in the space due to these assumptions of bad-faith intentions on the part of others in the space.

In these instances of democratic dysfunction, any intervention which succeeds in empowering the players to turn up and play the game could be considered a successful one. That is to say, the attunement model could offer a space for the players to overcome their initial negative preconceptions about the game, reject the potentially polarising influences that they may encounter and engage in a good faith game with others.

The rallying aspect of this metaphor (e.g.: the interaction between two polarised parties) can align directly with the idea of attunement via the process of sustaining political dialogue (English and Mahendran, 2025; 2021). That is to say, the rallying aspect of the game offers a direct metaphor for two parties engaging in direct dialogue with one another.

However, attunement is also a multi-level process that moves beyond an exclusive focus on individuals navigating moments of dissensus in direct discourse. To this end, another example of attunement success could be the players collaborating to reject the negative voices from one section of the crowd. That is to say, reject a group that is sharing disinformation about the game, umpire, other player, etc to develop a better understanding of the court dynamic. A relevant real-world example here are young citizens (one of the project's six target groups) and the potential for a political attunement intervention to create a context for them to understand social media groups and the information diet they are consuming. As found in WP4's research (D4.1) on how immigration-based everyday extremism is mainstreamed in young people are at risk in Sweden of encountering and sharing any of the following four crisis narratives: (1) Crises of impurity: Immigrants framed as 'contaminating' Swedish society ideologically and racially, (2) Conspiracy narratives: That there is a hidden agenda by elites to replace the Swedish population with immigrants, (3) Dystopian narratives: Immigration will lead to societal collapse, and (4) Existential threat: Immigrants were portrayed as a direct threat to the survival of the Swedish population. An intervention which allows young citizens to reject content presented as 'common-sense' thinking and collaborate (i.e.: attune to one another) to work towards recognising the inherent extremism behind seemingly 'mainstream' narratives on social media would be timely.

Figure 6. Visual Representation of the Political Attunement Model (Mahendran & English, 2025)

3.3 Integrating and Building the Conceptual Model

The following offers an overview of how work packages 2–6 are integrated into the model using the tennis metaphor.

WP 2: Line, Umpire and Net

Work package two focuses on the role of the line, umpire and net in the tennis metaphor – that is to say, the factors which enforce the pre-agreed rules (rule of law, regulatory rights prism) for the environment in which the players (be they nations, organisations, groups, or individuals) must navigate. To understand the function of regulations in this context, WP2 has developed a Regulatory-Rights Cases Toolkit (Deliverable 2.1) and Prisms (D2.2) for diagnosing environments of political and social extremism based on 16 specific cases. These insights will be disseminated to the target groups via Regulatory-Rights Interactive Website (D2.3) to enable them to apply the toolkit to both historical and contemporary cases.

WP 3: Coach

Whilst external to the players, the coaches are a forceable factor in creating the environment in which the game is played by focusing on pragmatic considerations (e.g.: a self-interested focus on the appropriate time to protect or attack). This is akin to the economic protectionist factors which influence potential training, investment, and autonomy at both the national, group, and individual levels. WP 3's interactive-orientated deliverables include an economic well-being behavioural toolkit (D3.2), an Offshore vs Reshore Gaming Tool (D3.4) (GCU and Slovenia), and an Interactive Map of transnational governance scenarios (D3.5). These are all tools which will contribute towards the Attunement Model's macro-level components and can be used by relevant stakeholders to understand the role of protectionist decision-making in creating a conducive environment for everyday extremism.

WP4: Crowd

How the crowd influence the players with their collective negative response to the 'game' – i.e.: how extreme narratives about the game that emerge from the public (via social media) can influence how individuals interact with others. Deliverable 4.1's report offers a visualisation of the prominent extremist narratives for key topics across Europe from a regional perspective (Northern; Central, Southern and Eastern Europe). WP4 also offers a three-country (Sweden, Austria, and Greece) report on trans-local articulation of extremism (D4.3), ethnographic case studies in these differing cultural and political contexts (D4.4) and model the extremist networks (D4.5). These deliverables offer real-world insights into the how 'the crowd' create, share and influence others with extreme narratives. Deliverable 4.6 then provides attunement advice with the Public Engagement Practitioner Handbook, which offers users guidance on how to mediate and/or moderate open engagement.

WP5: Ground

The ground surface has a fundamental impact on how the game is played and the potential limitations for the individual player. This is akin to how anthropological drivers (local, historical and cultural narratives) influence local communities' ideas

on what is politically possible. WP 5's starting point is to offer a framework paper on the emergence of oppositional anthropological drivers (D5.1). Deliverables (5.2 & 5.3) provide a Five Country Good Practice Case Studies Report for facilitating social dialogue for resilient democracies and multi-method, multi-disciplinary Five Country Methods Handbook. The former outlines successful social dialogue practices that may dissolve tendencies of polarizing and extremism, whilst the latter outlines principles for social dialogue interventions (including an attuned Social & Dialogue Toolkit based on good-practice settings. Finally, D5.4 offers Policy strategy briefs that translate local people's perspectives, experiences, knowledge into the European Democracy Action Plan (EDAP).

WP6: Oppositional Players

The psychological drivers which influence how the game is played and each player's capacity for maintaining the rally (as opposed to going for a volley). This can be enlarged to include nations and organisations (i.e.: not just individuals). There are four key deliverables in WP6 which will offer empirical evidence and applied knowledge towards understanding each player's 'capacity for attunement'. Deliverable 6.2, the WiDE Lens survey, explores how differences in Worldviews, Identifications and Disaffection influence potential for everyday extremism endorsement across 13 countries (N = 6,123). The 'Vote for Me' films (D6.3) offer insights into the potential for psychological drivers to evolve into more extreme political positions and this influences political endorsements. Deliverable 6.4, Four Country Pairing Study (Kosovo, Sweden England, and Scotland) explores which factors (e.g.: assumptions, political positions, attitude certainty) influence how polarised individuals sustain dialogue on the issue of immigration when in direct conversation. Finally, the I-Attune (D6.6) is a public-facing interactive developed to offer the public a tool for exploring their own Democratic Actor Positions, level of everyday extremism and how they can attune to those with differing political ideas. Together the outputs from these WP6 deliverables offer key insights into the factors that influence how successfully players can maintain a rally in an oppositional context with attunement. This may be by understanding how psychological drivers influence a person's capacity for endorsing extremism, how polarised individuals are able to sustain dialogue or how self-knowledge and guidance can create a context for attunement.

3.4. Using the model – Three-steps

Engaging with the model involves a three-step process which relates directly to the design of the overall OppAttune project’s three phases, outlined below in Figure 7.

1. Step one: what is the everyday extremism scenario?

2. Step two: how should everyday extremism be measured? what does successful attunement look like?

3. Step three: what is/are the appropriate attunement tool to achieve progress towards these outcomes?

It is worth noting that the full set of attunement toolkit have been adopted by WP7, to design bespoke tools which work within the respective country contexts and the specific scenarios identified by the partners within D7.1 and D7.2. Within WP7, the respective interventionist would decide on target group. So, it is important to be cautious about the status of the model, which is very much still within development. A final model will reflect feedback from the interventionist phase, which aims to limit the rise of extremist narratives and other indicators of everyday extremism.

Figure 7: Three Phases of the Attunement Model

1 Step 1 – What is the Everyday Extremism Scenario?

Evidence from the tracking phase suggests that key factors – which evolve to create everyday extremism relate to Polarisation, Protectionism, Prejudice and Disinformation.

2 Step 2 – How should Everyday Extremism be measured?

Work Package	Detect Everyday Extremism	Limit Everyday Extremism
WP2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Diagnostic Tool 1 – Determining Regulatory Rights Context - Interactive Map – Human Rights, Public Regulation, and Transnational Governance Scenarios (in collaboration with WP3). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Rule of Law/Democracy Pathways Prism - Diagnostic Tool 2 – Modes of Belonging - Diagnostic Tool 3 – Outcomes in Regulatory-Rights Pathways - Diagnostic Tool 4 – Forming Regulatory-Rights Prisms
WP4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Narrative Breaker – Detecting - Contextualising Narrative Tool - A(I)ttuning – AI Attunement Tool – Content (flag and frame content) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Narrative Breaker - Deconstructing - Emotional Check Tool - Media Literacy Tool - A(I)ttuning – AI Attunement Tool - Empathy (build empathy for others) - A(I)ttuning – AI Attunement Tool - Reflective Prompts (develop self-understanding) - A(I)ttuning – AI Attunement Tool - Role-Play (build democratic capacity)
WP5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Narrative Group Work - Psychoeducational Workshops - Reframing Disinformation Tool - Co-Created Attunement Games 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Narrative Group Work - Trust-Building Tool - Co-Created Games - Creating Conflict-Resolution Youth Workers - Gauging Ontological In/Security Tool
WP6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - On-line I-Attune self-test interactive - Four Country Pairing Research: Study A. (qualitative) - WiDE Lens – Brakes on Psychological drivers - Everyday Extremism scale - ‘Vote for Me’ – Political Mobilisation Tool - Shared Borders – more to this title? - BBC Film How quickly can online hate spread? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - On-line i-Attune self-test interactive - Dialogue Sustainment Attunement Tool - On-Line Interactive Do Your Relationships Need an Everyday Extremism Check? - ‘Vote for Me’ – Political Mobilisation Tool

Table 1. Detecting and Limiting Intervention Measures (Steps 2 and 3).

3**Step 3 –
Choosing the
appropriate
Attunement
Tool.**

Selecting the appropriate tool, relates to the key oppositional process that is being attuned and decision-making regarding what success looks like, for example it may be important to *diffuse* the extreme narratives, *deflect* the extreme narratives or *propagate* alternative counter-narratives. The user-guides outlined in Appendix A, give detailed procedural accounts of how to use each of the tools.

Discussion: Assumptions within the Attunement Model

When using the political attunement model, there are key parameters that need to be taken into consideration.

Assumptions of Dissensus and Discord.

One potential risk with the concept of attunement is the assumption that individuals ‘attuning’ to one another during political discourse is always best practice. If those in conversation with each other proceed harmoniously, then this is implicitly categorised as a troubling behaviour which must be ‘corrected’. In the political domain, this is especially relevant as there are a complex interconnectivity of motivations and influencing factors, as explored in OppAttune deliverables (e.g.: historical legacies in D2.2, current inequalities in D5.4, future precarities, D6.6) which create reasons why a person (or group) may feel that attunement as a process is not creating change quickly enough. In these scenarios, individual or collective narratives foreground the idea that only by becoming a disruptive force can meaningful political change occur. In such circumstances, understanding the need for a political attunement intervention must revert to the defining features of everyday extremism by answering the following question: are the intentions of those who do not wish to attune manifesting as political dialogue or actions which limit the democratic rights of others and/or possess symbolic violence at anyone who disagrees? If the answer to this question is yes, then within the model, this becomes a question of balancing rights to radical political action against regulatory pathways (see, D2.2). Ideally to create the opportunity for self-reflexivity on the part of those rejecting the idea of attunement.

Standpoint & reflexivity

A related challenge to this process of identifying everyday extremism is the political bias of users of the attunement model, who are likely to have their own worldviews, identifications and goals which influence the standpoints they take towards the political attunement they are engaged in. Firstly, in their very decision that a particular scenario requires attunement. The scientific and research community, which is one of the key target groups for the attunement model may well approach the attunement model with different goals when compared to practitioner organisations. Whilst it is highly contested as to whether this is a positive or negative factor in terms of research development (Burmila, 2021), for a project exploring political extremism, it is important that partners possess a level of reflexivity when using the political attunement model. Specifically, the limitations in any one academic’s capacity for assessing what real-world contexts require an attunement intervention and how these decisions are finalised. Within OppAttune’s final limiting phase, led by Gordon Sammut and Joana Ricarte, the importance of the consortium meetings in which both academics and NGO workers collaborate to understand the ‘on the ground’ realities of the political climate in the areas that were designated for fieldwork.

Political literacy and capacity for democracy

In terms of the practical application of attunement interventions, the focus is on offering specific target groups relevant tools for their context. For example, WP 5’s Narrative Group Work or WP 6’s Dialogue Sustainment Attunement Tool are designed to be used by frontline practitioners working with young people. As such, the intervention design on both of these tools assumes a certain level of competence working with young people in the first instance as a prerequisite for applying an attunement intervention. That is to say, these interventions are not accessible to the ‘layperson’ in terms of immediate application without training or experience. However, tools designed for a specific purpose and context do also offer a welcome specificity for those skilled and experienced in the context of the intervention.

Conclusion

The political attunement model presented within the report, represents considerable collective effort and innovation visualised in Figure 6. It remains very much within an initial phase as a means of limiting everyday extremism. The Political Attunement Model and its tools provide a pathway within democracy, which builds democratic capacity to navigate contested context and vexed political issues such as immigration, vaccination, and climate-change. It builds on the analysis and findings that has occurred during the first two phases of the OppAttune project, in this respect the attunement model is very much a transdisciplinary model which, as the review which opens this report demonstrates, builds on four traditions which inform collective understanding of the potential of political attunement to enable citizens across Europe and beyond to develop their political literacy and democratic capacity.

The metaphor of a game of tennis enables democratic actors, at whatever level to explore how positional play, acknowledgement of the other's legitimacy, and sustained engagement can help limit everyday extremism and strengthen democratic capacity. The model through its steps enables users to recognise emerging extreme narratives, how to stay in dialogue when worldviews collide and how to build skills that support "living democracy" in everyday settings.

The model, toolkit and stages are being used by eight partners on either side of the European Union's borders, and the evaluation of the model will occur within the limiting phase of the OppAttune project.

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Appendix A: Attunement Tool-Kits Developed for WP7

Regulatory- Rights Attunement Tools – Tool-Kit

User Guide

WP2 - Pathways Within Democracy – Rights & Protections

Within the Political Attunement Model for **Limiting Everyday Extremism and Building Democratic Capacity**, Tools from Work Package 2 are referred to as Regulatory-Rights Attunement Tools. Once you have established the Everyday Extremism Scenario (Step 1) and explored possible limiting approaches (Step 2) then this guide will provide you with a set of proposed Rights and Rules Tools which have been established in the tracking phase of OppAttune. Work Package also provides a set of 16 detailed case studies which can inform the intervention. Using this guide aims to enable you to design a bespoke rights and rules tool which fits your objectives, the context, and specific case for intervention.

Regulatory-Rights Tools can be understood within the political attunement tennis metaphor relating to the lines, the agreed rules of the games as well as the ongoing role of the lines umpire to call whether the ball is out, player is at fault, crowd needs to be quiet etc. For example, these tools work with self-other relationships, real/symbolic threat, cognitive closure, polarisation, political mobilisation and followership, dehumanisation, worldviews and identifications. Key outcome measures include the Everyday Extremism, Followership measures and Sustained Dialogue.

Regulatory-Rights Attunement Tools aim to enable interest groups and other players to make claims and equally can be used if you wish to explore understanding of the rule of law. Finally, they can be used in interventions where there is an issue around freedom of speech.

The prism developed by WP2 focuses on three key steps – Context, Belonging & Outcome.

1. Diagnostic Tool 1 – Determining Regulatory Rights Context
2. Diagnostic Tool 2 – Modes of Belonging
3. Diagnostic Tool 3 – Outcomes in Regulatory-Rights Pathways
4. Diagnostic Tool 4 – Forming Regulatory-Rights Prisms
5. Interactive Map – Human Rights, Public Regulation, and Transnational Governance Scenarios (in collaboration with WP3).

Full procedural guides on using the WP2's toolkit and the interactive map from WP3 are available on AUPs site and also on the OppAttune site.

WP2 Deliverables

D2.1 16 Regulatory-Rights Cases Toolkit for diagnosing environments of political and social extremism based on 16 cases. AUP, Bilgi, OU & UCY (Month 9).

D2.2 16 Regulatory-Rights Prisms based on cases into specific types. AUP, Bilgi, OU & UCY (month 11).

D2.3 Regulatory-Rights Interactive Website – for dissemination – 16 cases which enable six target groups practitioners/policymakers to apply the toolkit to other historical and contemporary cases. Also, for research community purposes for teaching the history of extremist narratives. To be included in Attunement model. AUP, Bilgi, OU & UCY (month 15)

Examples

18 case studies are available to WP7 to support the development of interventions. as evidence the outcome of past cases.

Examples

18 case studies are available to WP7 to support the development of interventions. as evidence the outcome of past cases.

Tool	Source	When to Use	Key Attunement Process: Line Umpiring	Outcome
Diagnostic Tool 1 Determining Regulatory Rights Context	D2.2 & D2.3	Hate Speech Ensuring Freedom of Speech		
Diagnostic Tool 2 Modes of Belonging	D2.2 & D2.3	Protecting free expression against violent threat		
Diagnostic Tool 3 Outcomes in Regulatory-Rights Pathways	D2.2 & D2.3	Protecting free expression against violent threat		
Diagnostic Tool 4 Forming Regulatory-Rights Prisms	D2.2 & D2.3	Protecting free expression against violent threat		
Interactive Map Interactive Map – Human Rights, Public Regulation, and Transnational Governance Scenarios (in collaboration with WP3).	D3.5	Protectionism and Hybrid Governance	WP3 tools relate to coaching each player on their decision-making	

Table 2. WP2: Attunement Tool-Kits and Applications

Parameters to Consider when Using the Regulatory-Rights Tools

Tools were developed based on evidence gathered across 18 cases, the WiDE Lens survey involves 13 countries and the full country reports are available. Regulatory-Rights Attunement Tools relate mostly to the interest claims of specific groups. For more support on how to use the tools please contact

- In situations where the intervention involves mediating between two oppositional groups, who are likely to stay as groups over the long term. The person/entity is a leader, or in some sort of governance role.
- In situations where a group requires further support to make their right claims and are being challenged by another group. (often about levelling up playing field/countering populist dynamics).
- In situations where the group needs to reinforce the regulations on the situation.

Within the context of WP7s activities these tools provide a valuable means of exploring rule of law and where the lines are, with participants who may well be operating in post-truth and disinformation scenarios.

Limiting Mobilisation Attunement Tools – Tool-Kit

User Guide

WP4 - Media, Machines & Mobilization

Working with the Attunement Model – Mobilisation Tools arising out of WP4 can be understood as establishing the likely narratives within the crowd which are influencing the relative democratic capacities to play of both parties. WP4 tracks the evolution of online-offline hybrid narratives. The work package has articulated their trajectory and the unlikely coalitions of people that occur. Mobilisation tools from WP4 can be used to capture and limit mobilising extreme narratives which are influencing the flexibility and possibility of positional play of both players. To go further, the tools created from WP4 will influence the understanding of reality and truth of everyone involved, players, the crowd, audiences watching on their screens. In this sense mobilising extreme narratives can be understood to interpolate the positional capacity of everyone involved. Using this guide aims to enable you to design a bespoke mobilisation-related tool which fits the context, and specific case for intervention.

Within the attunement model, the authors, Tina Askanus, Miriam Haselbacher, Ursula Reeger and Jullietta Stoencheva explain “WP4 speaks to the meso level. The meso level is concerned with group dynamics, hence, the question how people come together, how they engage with each other and how they come to form collective entities” .

WP4 tool aims to develop democratic citizens who are digitally literate and can understand and unpack mobilising extreme narratives, how they work and how to limit them and how to counteract them.

Tools

1. Narrative Breaker – Detecting Everyday Extreme Narratives
2. Narrative Breaker – Deconstructing Everyday Extremist Narrative
3. Contextualising Narrative Tool
4. Emotional Impact Tool
5. Media Literacy Tool
6. A(I)ttuning – AI Attunement Tool Empathy
7. A(I)ttuning – AI Attunement Tool – Content
8. A(I)ttuning – AI Attunement Tool Role-Play

Each of these tools require a certain amount of time. Which will be determined as a discussion between the WP7 team and WP5.

WP 4 Deliverables

D 4.1 Report including visualisation providing an overview of prominent extremist narratives emerging around the key topics of the project across Europe from a regional perspective (Northern; Central, Southern and Eastern Europe) (Building on literature review and secondary data) (Task 5.1, Month 9)

D 4.2 Three Country Translocal Articulation of Extremism & Visualisation Reports of translocal narratives (Sweden, Austria, and Greece) (Task 5.2 Month 18)

D 4.3 OppAttune Media, Machines & Mobilisation Blog documenting field work at major events across the sites of analysis; researchers sharing stories, testimonies, videos, photos of material artefacts preliminary analysis etc. (Task 5.3, deliverables running continuously from month 3-30)

D 4.4 Three ethnographic case studies in Greece, Sweden and Austria (Task 5.3, month 30)

D 4.5 Modelling Networks of Extremist Narratives Report – (Task 5.4, month 6 & month 22)

D 4.6 Public Engagement Practitioner Handbook: to mediate and/or moderate open engagement – including Artificial Intelligence handbook (Task 5.5, month 30)

Key elements of attunement

Positional responses, acknowledging the other, resisting mobilisation from the crowd, being buoyed by the crowd, tactical and strategic decision and continual rallying, sustaining the rally is a specific element of attunement – but attunement is necessarily a multi-level process, which relates to the crowds, ability to withstand disinformation, resistance mobilisation, how to access the rules, accepting that the ball is out, as well as the right to appeal.

Parameters to Consider when Using the Limiting Mobilisation Tools

Tools were developed based on evidence gathered in Sweden, Austria, Bulgaria and Greece. They mostly relate to two target audiences – the general public and media actors. A full account of the rationale for each of the tools is provided by WP4 below in Appendix 1.

Limiting Mobilisation tools – relate to partner specialisms, as follows:

Malmo University – Media Analysis

Vienna Austrian – urban environments/ethnographic approaches

Slovenia – big data, data modelling

Open University – general public in Greece (WP4.4)

Tool	Source	When to Use	Key Attunement Process: Line Umpiring	Outcome
Narrative Breaker – Detecting	D4.1 & D4.2	Polarisation within the public	Acknowledging the Other	Limit development of polarising narratives.
Narrative Breaker – Deconstructing	D4.x	Polarisation within the public	Resisting Disinformation	Understanding Horizontal and Vertical Populism
Contextualising Narrative Tool	D4.x	Case construction in each city/location	Tactical positioning in own context	Understanding Local Terrain
Emotional Check Tool	D4.x	Understanding Divisive disinformation	Resisting affective mobilisation from crowd	Lower defence mechanisms
Media Literacy Tool	D4.x	To build capacity of public to understand Divisive disinformation – e.g. conspiracies	Resisting Mobilisation Strategic and tactical positioning	Democratic Resilience
A(I)ttuning – AI Attunement Tool Empathy	D4.x	To Build Empathic Opposite Orientation	Acknowledging the Other Understanding Self-Motivations	Empathy & Perspective-Taking Countering De-humanisation
A(I)ttuning – AI Attunement Tool – Content	D4.x	To flag and reframe polarising & discriminatory content	Moderation	De-escalation
A(I)ttuning – AI Attunement Tool Reflective Prompts	D4.1, D4.2	To build Self-Understanding	Self-coaching	Democratic Resilience
A(I)ttuning – AI Attunement Tool Role-Play	D4.4	To build Democratic Capacity	Player Dynamics	Democratic Capacity & Sustained Dialogue

Table 3. WP4: Attunement Tool-Kits and Applications

Input from WP4 for the attunement model

Tina Askanius, Miriam Haselbacher, Ursula Reeger, Jullietta Stoencheva

Within WP4 *Media, Machines, and Mobilisations*, we have focused so far on OppAttune's first objective of tracking the evolution of extreme political narratives. In the first deliverable, we identified key topics around which extremist narratives occur and have shown how these narratives exploit societal fears and uncertainties, particularly during crises like the COVID-19 pandemic. In the second deliverable, we focused on the EU elections to decipher translocal articulations of everyday extremism. In this latter report, we presented a relational model for understanding everyday extremism that unfolds along three analytical continuums: translocal-local, online-offline, mundane-extreme.

The results of the empirical work we have conducted so far have provided us with valuable insights that we believe should inform the attunement model. One key finding is the **need for context sensitivity** – attunement should consider local context and recognise the unique social, cultural, and political dynamics that influence how extremism manifests in different regions, localities and communities. Hence, a certain adaptability is essential in order to ensure that the tools and the model are effective in diverse environments. Additionally, our research strongly indicates the **hybridity of spaces** and the intricate connection between online and offline realms. This underscores the need to approach attunement as a two-way process, where both spheres are considered equally, seeing how everyday extremist narratives circulate across digital platforms and local settings. Another crucial aspect of attunement is the need to recognise and engage with the **transnational visual language and codes** specific to digital cultures. As extremism often manifests through visual ephemera – symbols, memes, and coded language – attunement models should incorporate strategies to analyse, decode and deconstruct these constantly evolving forms of expression. Corresponding to this, it is essential to **identify and deconstruct crisis narratives** that fuel extremism, especially those that exploit moments of societal vulnerability. Lastly, we also see an ongoing importance of understanding processes of othering and **binary “us vs. them” constructs**. These divisive frameworks underlie polarising and hostile discourses, and addressing them is crucial for fostering more inclusive and constructive conversations in both digital and offline spaces. Summarising the insights from our empirical work, we suggest that attunement models should be dynamic, responsive, and multifaceted to address the complex and evolving nature of extremism in today's interconnected world.

Within the attunement model, WP 4 speaks to the meso level. The meso level is concerned with group dynamics, hence, the question how people come together, how they engage with each other and how they come to form collective entities. Within our empirical work, the most important examples include social movements, protesters or ordinary citizens for the offline world and online communities. Within the tennis metaphor, WP 4 is the crowd. The crowd is not a passive entity; it is an active participant both online and offline, shaping the atmosphere and influencing the direction of the game. Offline, e.g. at sidelines of the court, the crowd's energy, through physical presence and vocal support, can sway the momentum of the players and amplify specific narratives. Similarly, online, the crowd's digital engagement – through comments, shares, and memes – creates a virtual space of influence, and can shape the public discourse and amplify certain viewpoints. Hence, the tools we suggest below target groups and on- and offline communities, taking into consideration the specific characteristics of on- and offline spheres.

Based on these reflections, we provide preliminary input below on what we see as two potential tools that could be developed for the attunement model:

Tool 1: Narrative Breaker – Deconstructing everyday extremist narratives

This tool focuses on detecting and deconstructing everyday extremist narratives, which often appear under the guise of coded imagery, irony, humor and otherwise nebulous and ambiguous content.

We propose an interactive digital tool designed to help individuals, educators, and organisations to identify, analyse, and deconstruct everyday extremist narratives. For example, the tool could use visual content to empower users to critically engage with potentially harmful narratives. The tool should promote active engagement and reflective learning. In the abovementioned example, users could exercise deconstruction of narratives within images by answering a series of guiding questions, i.e.:

- *What symbols or imagery are present in this image? (e.g., flags, hand gestures, symbols, logos)*
- *What emotions does the image evoke, and why might it be designed to do so? Does it imply or make references to notions of (existential) crisis? What is at stake and for whom?*
- *Who is being portrayed or targeted in this image? What message is conveyed about them? (who is the out-group? who is the in-group?)*
- *Does the image convey violent or harmful messages? Is violence or hostility directed towards certain groups?*
- *What larger historical or political context is this image drawing on?*

After the self-guided analysis, users should be presented with a context-driven explanation of the image's potential extremist or harmful messages. This explanation includes:

- *A breakdown of the symbols and imagery used, explaining their specific relevance in extremist narratives*
- *An exploration of the emotional appeal of the image, showing how it might manipulate feelings such as fear, anger, or resentment to galvanise a particular ideological stance/extremist subject position.*
- *Insight into the political, social, or cultural context behind the image, discussing how certain visual representations are designed to promote a binary worldview, create “us vs. them” distinctions, or trigger crisis narratives.*
- *A reflection on the audience's role in interpreting and responding to these images, emphasising the importance of context in avoiding misinterpretation or manipulation.*

In the example above, this tool can serve as both an educational tool and a preventive mechanism, equipping users with the media literacy and critical skills necessary to detect and resist the influence of extremist visual content. By actively engaging with the imagery (e.g. memes, comic strips etc.) they encounter, ordinary citizens will develop a deeper understanding of how online extremism works and how to respond to it. This will foster critical thinking and contribute to a more informed and media literate general public that can engage in constructive dialogue rather than be swayed by divisive, emotionally charged imagery.

Tool 2: A(I)ttuning – AI informed attunement tools targeting online debates and hate speech

We further propose utilizing recent technological developments to create AI-informed attunement tools for automatic detection of harmful content in online debates on social media. There are multiple possibilities for the use of AI on social media, but below we list some suggestions for where we think AI-informed attunement tools could be applied:

Empathy-building interventions

We propose a tool that analyses the language and tone of online posts and comments to identify when the conversation may be escalating into hostility or polarisation. It could suggest empathetic responses or present prompts that encourage users to consider the other side's point of view. For example, when the user types a comment that includes violent and hostile content, the tool could flag these and suggest a more empathetic response or ask the user to consider the other side's experience or feelings. For instance, "How might someone with a different view feel about this issue?" or "Consider this person's background before responding."

Content moderation with a focus on de-escalation

AI-driven tools could not only flag inappropriate content but also offer suggestions for reframing comments in more neutral or constructive ways. Hence, instead of immediate removal, some posts could receive soft interventions that encourage dialogue – such as asking for clarification or providing alternative perspectives that promote constructive discussion.

Post-engagement reflection prompts

After an online debate or conversation, users could receive feedback or reflection prompts encouraging them to think about their engagement. For example: "Did you feel your comments contributed to a positive discussion?" or "What could you have said differently to avoid escalating the conversation?" Tools could provide users with a summary of their tone, language, and whether their comments contained emotionally charged words or inflammatory language, prompting them to reconsider their approach in future interactions.

Gamification community moderation

Another idea for this tool would be to allow users to put themselves in the position of community moderators and asks them to set rules and norms of engagement. For example, users could be confronted with online debates and asked to perform the role of the moderator and to intervene when discussions start to become hostile, aiming to uphold democratic dialogue standards.

Living Democracy Attunement Tools – Tool-Kit

User Guide

WP5 - Extremism and Living Democracies

Within the Political Attunement Model for limiting Everyday Extremism and Building Democratic Capacity, Tools from Work Package 5 are referred to as Living Democracy Tools. Once you have established the Everyday Extremism Scenario (Step 1) and explored possible limiting approaches (Step 2) then this guide will provide you with a set of proposed Living Democracy Tools which have been established in the tracking phase of OppAttune. Using this guide aims to enable you to design a bespoke living democracy tool which fits the context, and specific case for intervention.

Living Democracy Tools can be understood as establishing the presuppositional ground, the lived realities which explain why various players and the crowd are taking the oppositional positions they are taking and the extent to which they are entrenched within cultural and practice norms. Living Democracy tools aim to build resilient democracies.

1. Gauging Ontological In/Security Tool
2. Polarisation Us & Them – Understanding Vertical & Horizontal Populism Tool - Educating the public.
3. Reframing Disinformation Tool – Narratives.
4. Trust-Building Tool (orientating yourself within the process)
5. Co-Created Games – (using ethnography research)
6. Narrative Group Work (NGW)
7. Creating Conflict-Resolution Youth Workers
8. Psychoeducational Workshops

Each of these tools require a certain amount of time. Which will be determined as a discussion between the WP7 team and WP5.

Living Democracy Tools

All these tools are for group work with oppositional groups and narratives relating to understanding young people as existing within living contexts, containing deeply-rooted oppositional political narratives.

All these tools are for group work with oppositional groups and narratives relating to understanding young people as existing within living contexts. These contexts contain deeply-rooted oppositional political narratives. The role of living democracy tools can be understood as playing two key roles – levelling the playing field, through understanding the practices of all players, as well as increasing the capacity for positional play of both oppositional entities, with specific reference to marginalised players, who face clear power asymmetries. Use of Living democracy tools can support participants to be able to resist being mobilised by crowd dynamics and engage in tactical decision making to further their goals.

Tool	Source	When to Use	Key Attunement Process: Line Umpiring	Outcome
Trust-Building Tool	D5.1	Polarisation within Young People	Acknowledging the other player Rallying (ideally)	Increased Dialogue
Us/Them Dynamic	D5.2	Polarisation within Young People	Resisting mobilisation from the crowd	Understanding Horizontal and Vertical Populism
Reframing Disinformation Tool	D5.2	Disinformation	Resisting mobilisation	Democratic Resilience
Narrative Group Work (NGW)	D5.2	Misinformation	Resisting being buoyed by the crowd	Limit development of counter-narratives
Co-Created Games	D5.2 & D5.3	Misinformation (inc. Conspiracies)	Tactical and Strategic Decision-Making	Lowers defence mechanism increases playful engagement with other – even when political stakes are high
Gauging Ontological In/Security Tool	D5.1	Destructive Bordering (e.g. globalisation, protecting borders)	Accepting the Rules of the Game	Recognition of the Other
Creating Conflict-Resolution Youth Workers	D5.3	Polarisation	Increasing Capacity for Positional play	Equipping new agents of change
Psychoeducational Workshops	D5.3	Intolerance & Discrimination	Increasing Capacity for Positional play	Empathy & Perspective-Taking Building Inclusive Self-Confidence and Identity

Table 4. WP5: Attunement Tool-Kits and Applications

Successful limiting of Everyday Extremism using these tools should lead to increased democratic resilience through what is termed by the WP5 partnership as social resonance. Social resonance can facilitate the emergence of heightened interpersonal understanding of the views of others across wide differences, as well as emotional empathy – and self-reflection/inter-reflection – in relation to their personal situation(s) and lived biographical trajectories (Rottman et al (2025) D5.3 Five Country Methods Handbook).

Parameters to Consider when Using the Limiting Mobilisation Tools

Tools were developed based on evidence gathered in Turkey, Germany, Portugal, Serbia and Bosnia & Herzegovina. They mostly relate to two target audiences – young people, and the general public.

Living Democracy tools – relate to partner specialisms, as follows:

Cultures Interactive – young people, teachers, town hall meetings, (engaged public etc) specific target groups.

Ozy University - Oz – engaged public, community members (local contexts).

PRONI – professionals, policy-makers,

Coimbra – general public, young citizens (majority students), researchers.

They derive from the following deliverables.

D5.1 Framework paper Document, report PU - Public 14

D5.2 Five country good practice case studies report – Document, report PU - Public 22 D5.3 Five country methods handbook Document, report PU – Public 24

D5.4 Policy strategy briefs Document, report PU – Public 26

Prepared by Kesi Mahendran & Anthony English
Attunement Phase - April 2025.

Public Dialogue Attunement Tools – Tool-Kit

User Guide

WP6 - Attuning Public Dialogue & Narratives – Psychological Drivers

Within the **Political Attunement Model for limiting Everyday Extremism and Building Democratic Capacity**, Tools from Work Package 6 are referred to as *Public Dialogue* Attunement Tools. Once you have established the Everyday Extremism Scenario (Step 1) and explored possible limiting approaches (Step 2) then this guide will provide you with a set of proposed Public Dialogue Tools which have been established in the tracking phase of OppAttune. Using this guide aims to enable you to design a bespoke public dialogue tool which fits your objectives, the context, and specific case for intervention.

Public Dialogue Tools can be understood as relating to the two or more players involved in the attunement process, but equally it is possible to intervene in relation to the ball. For example, these tools work with self-other relationships, real/symbolic threat, cognitive closure, polarisation, political mobilisation and followership, dehumanisation, worldviews and identifications. Key outcome measures include the Everyday Extremism, Followership measures and Sustained Dialogue.

Public Dialogue tools aim to build political literacy and democratic capacity for public dialogue in oppositional political scenarios e.g. elections, referenda, and everyday political life.

1. Everyday Extremism Scale.
2. Vote for Me – Political Mobilisation
3. WiDE Lens Survey Tool – capturing psychological drivers.
4. Sustaining Dialogue Attunement Tool
5. I-attune – online self-test interactive.
6. Do Your Relationships Need an Everyday Extremism Check? Online self-test interactive.
7. BBC Film - How quickly can online hate spread? (7.00min)

In addition, there are two tools which relate to the psychology of being an online sleuth, which could support work to dismantle disinformation and conspiracy theories.

1. Are you an Online Detective? Online self-test interactive
2. BBC Film - Why are we obsessed with being armchair detectives?

Each of these tools can be completed within three months, including before and after a political event. All seven public dialogue tools can be used face-to-face or on-line. Please feel free to contact relevant leads from KCSS, Malta, OU, and Panteion regarding using the Public Dialogue tools after discussions within WP7.

WP 6 Deliverables

D6.1. Everyday Extremism

To create an Everyday Extremism Scale – EES (UoM) designed in Malta and tested within UK, Greece, Kosovo, and Malta which enables benchmarking of people's understanding of what constitutes political extremism and the conditions by which they would adopt or share extreme narratives.

D6.2. WiDE Lens Survey

Understanding how differences in Worldviews, Identifications and Disaffection influence potential for everyday extremism endorsement across different cultural and political contexts (N = 6,123) in 13 European countries.

D6.3. 'Vote for Me' films

To understand how psychological drivers have the potential to evolve into violent political transformations using political actors, OU researchers in WP6 developed Vote for Me films across two nations (UK and Greece).

D6.4. Four Country Pairing Study

Explore what factors (e.g.: assumptions, political positions, attitude certainty) influence how polarised individuals sustain dialogue on the issue of immigration when in direct conversation (N = 42). Kosovo (Pristina), Scotland (Edinburgh), Sweden (Malmö), and England (Manchester).

D6.5. Attunement Model

Develop the Attunement Model out of results from studies across and toolkits across the other work packages to create the opportunity for the public to develop democratic resilience to oppositional thinking.

D6.6. I-Attune interactive

Creation of a public-facing interactive which allows the public (UK-centred but with trans-national potential) to explore their Democratic Actor Positions, level of everyday extremism and how they can attune to those with differing political ideas.

Tool	Source	When to Use	Key Attunement Process: Line Umpiring	Outcome
Everyday Extremism scale	D6.1	Behavioural Intentions	Measure of potential to support everyday extremism	Gauging acceptable level of everyday extremism
WiDE Lens Survey	D6.2	Psychological drivers	Gauging worldviews and context. Acknowledging another's worldview perspective, position	Provides country level psychological drivers.
'Vote for Me' - Political Mobilisation Tool	D6.3	Political mobilisation	Degree of independence and influence	Insights into followership
Sustaining Dialogue Attunement Tool	D6.4	Political Polarisation	Self-other relationships / Rallying (keeping the ball in play)	Maintaining democratic parameters (respect for the other player)
On-line I-Attune self-test interactive	D6.7	Polarisation & Building Democratic Capacity	Self-coaching & Dynamics between players	Attuning between contrasting players
On-Line Interactive Do Your Relationships Need an Everyday Extremism Check?	N/A	Political Polarisation	Self-coaching on player flexibility and rigidity	User-Friendly Interactive to explore six aspects of Everyday Extremism
BBC Film How quickly can online hate spread?	N/A	Conspiracy Thinking, Hate Speech & Dehumanisation	Movement of the ball beyond the lines	Increased awareness of public responsibility for everyday extremism

Table 5. WP6: Attunement Tool-Kits and Applications

Parameters to Consider when Using the Limiting Mobilisation Tools

Tools were developed based on evidence gathered in UK, Malta, Kosovo, Sweden and Greece within the deliverables outlined below. The WiDE Lens survey involves 13 countries and the full country reports are available.

Public Dialogue Attunement Tools mostly relate to two target audiences:

- The general public, D6.1 (Gordon Sammut & Rebecca Mifsud, D6.2 (Antonis Dimakis, Xenia Chrysochoou)
- Public and young people D6.4 (Anthony English)
- Public, media influencers and political actors D6.3 (Evangelia Vergouli, Kesi Mahendran & Evangelos Ntontis).

Appendix B: Political Mobilisation & Followership Attunement Tool (the “Vote for Me” Films)

Introduction

This Political Mobilisation and Followership Attunement Tool is designed to support the understanding of political mobilisation and followership. It is part of a broader suite of Public Dialogue Attunement Tools developed by WP6 to be used in interventions by WP7. The tool made available to WP7 partners originates from a PhD research project on political mobilisation, conducted by Evangelia Vergouli under the supervision of Prof. Kesi Mahendran and Dr. Evangelos Ntontis at the Open University. The research team, working within the field of social and political psychology, collaborated closely with the film production company, Damn Fine Media, which developed the scripts, filmed, and produced the videos in ongoing dialogue with the team.

The “Vote for me” Films

The five “Vote for me” films, each lasting approximately 3 minutes, serve as stimuli materials that can be used with a variety of target groups relating to the OppAttune project including young people, voting age publics, practitioners and potentially politicians. They use a dialogical design which moves beyond small vignettes by presenting fully embodied political archetypes, designed to evoke engagement through rhetorical style, policy content, and communication dynamics. As such, their use is intended to facilitate dialogical exchange between viewers and the portrayed political leaders.

Nationalist

Technocrat

Progressive

Conservative

Revolutionary

How were the “Vote for me” films developed?

Damn Fine Media received a comprehensive brief from the principal researcher. This brief detailed the key characteristics of each political leader archetype, emphasizing both rhetorical strategies and elements of embodied communication, such as speech delivery, body language, and dress code. The development of this brief, which guided the production of the “Vote for me” films, was informed by both top-down and bottom-up strategies.

Work conducted by colleagues within the [Public Dialogue Psychology Collaboratory](#) on populism was particularly valuable in shaping our understanding of political communication and presentation styles. Drawing on this foundation, the research progressed in two key stages.

In the first stage, Evangelia conducted a scoping review of existing literature across the fields of social and political psychology, political science, and communication studies. The aim was to explore how political party representatives' mobilisation discourse had previously been studied, with a specific focus on whether political figures could be categorised not by traditional affiliations (e.g., left or right), but rather by their rhetorical strategies and communication styles.

In the second stage, video footage of real political leaders from across Europe was collected. This footage was analysed and compared with findings from earlier research on political communication. Through this iterative process, the research team identified five distinct archetypes of political leaders (see stills from the videos above).

Evangelia then developed the brief for the film production company, outlining the defining features of each archetype. This included the typical arguments they used—particularly around immigration—their rhetorical style, and their modes of delivery. Real-world examples of politicians embodying each archetype were provided, along with links to relevant video clips.

The final set of videos features five fully realised political archetypes, each portrayed in distinct contexts (e.g., a formal podium, a street interview, a podcast setting). These portrayals highlight the unique rhetoric, arguments, and delivery styles that characterise each archetype, offering a dynamic tool for understanding the diversity of political communication.

How were the “Vote for me” films originally used?

The “Vote for Me” films were originally used as stimulus materials by Evangelia Vergouli in her PhD study with citizens in the UK ($N = 20$) and Greece ($N = 20$). The videos were part of a semi-structured interview in which participants were prompted to discuss their political preferences and voting behaviour. Specifically, the interviewer invited participants to watch one video at a time (in random order) and then asked follow-up questions (e.g., “*What are your first thoughts and impressions?*”, “*Does this politician appeal to you? Why?*” — see examples of questions below). In interviews with Greek participants, the films were shown with Greek subtitles.

This research design opens space for dialogical agency, shifting participants from narrators of fixed identities to co-creators of political meaning—engaging in storytelling, decision-making, imagined future orientations, and the negotiation of value conflicts within a structured yet open-ended format.

Rather than extracting fixed accounts, the method co-produces knowledge through layered, reflexive exchanges between participants, political stimuli, and interviewer. In doing so, it challenges traditional asymmetries between researcher and participant, recognising participants as epistemic agents capable of articulating complex political imaginaries. Finally, it offers textured, multi-voiced insights into the dynamics through which extreme political narratives gain traction—or are resisted—in citizens' political discourse.

Target Groups

The five films can be effectively used in interventions carried out by either NGOs, Universities, collectives or individual activists in both online and offline social spaces (e.g., through sharing on social media platforms and inviting people to comment, through focus groups, online interviews, etc.).

How to use the videos when doing interventions to limit everyday extremism

- The deliverable can be effectively employed in any intervention aimed at engaging citizens with political leaders' communication (e.g., to understand their political and voting decision-making, their capacity to sustain dialogue with diverse political narratives as expressed by the archetypes, their boundary making regarding what political narratives they find acceptable or extreme). As all political figures featured in the films express their views on immigration policies, the videos can also serve as valuable stimuli for exploring public discourse on immigration.
- These videos are suitable for both online and in-person settings, provided their use is supported by a clear structure and rationale. For example, in citizen interviews, viewers should receive clear instructions outlining how the session will unfold, how many videos they will watch, the general content of the videos, and the types of questions they will be asked.
- The order in which the videos are shown can be randomised.
- To maintain viewer engagement and reduce cognitive load, we recommend that the videos are not presented all at once. Instead, show one video at a time, pausing after each to ask follow-up questions. This approach promotes reflection and more meaningful responses.
- In the principal researcher's study, participants were not informed of the political archetypes' "titles" (e.g., progressive, technocrat, revolutionary, nationalist, conservative). This was a deliberate methodological choice, intended to encourage participants to engage freely with the content and generate their own interpretations, without being influenced by predefined labels. The goal was to promote open-ended association and dialogical engagement. However, this approach is not prescriptive for future uses. Whether or not to disclose the titles should be determined based on the specific objectives of the intended use and should be thoughtfully considered as part of the design process.
- When using the videos in national contexts outside the UK, it is recommended that the scripts be translated and subtitled by a native speaker to ensure linguistic and cultural accuracy. Tools such as VEED.IO can be used to add subtitles.

Communicating Findings

The research findings will be presented by the Evangelia Vergouli at the **British Psychological Society's Qualitative Methods in Psychology 2025 Conference** (Title: "*Political Mobilisation and Everyday Extremism: Power-Sharing Dialogical Methodologies for Citizens' Meaning-Making Across the UK and Greece*"), as well as the **International Society of Political Psychology Annual Meeting 2025** (Title: "*Dialogical dynamics of political mobilisation and followership: Exploring everyday extremism in citizens' political decision-making*"). The full analysis will be subsequently developed in detail in the principal researcher's PhD thesis and submitted for peer review in a thematically relevant academic journal.

Attribution guidelines

The use of D6.3 films should be referenced to the following references:

Vergouli, E., Mahendran, K., & Ntontis, E. (2025). D6.3. Followership & Political Mobilisation Attunement Tool (the “Vote for me” Films).

Vergouli, E., Mahendran, K., & Ntontis, E. (2025, July 6). *Dialogical dynamics of political mobilisation and followership: Exploring everyday extremism in citizens’ political decision-making*. [Conference presentation]. International Society of Political Psychology Annual Meeting, Prague, Czech Republic.

Vergouli, E., Mahendran, K., & Ntontis, E. (2025, July 10). *Political Mobilisation and Everyday Extremism: Power-Sharing Dialogical Methodologies for Citizens’ Meaning-Making Across the UK and Greece* [Conference presentation]. The British Psychological Society Qualitative Methods in Psychology Conference, Leeds, UK.

Please add the following attribution in any written or oral report:

The “Vote for me” films were developed by OppAttune researchers Evangelia Vergouli, Kesi Mahendran, and Evangelos Ntontis to facilitate the exploration of dialogue between political leaders and citizens. Their production was undertaken by Damn Fine Media.

When using this public dialogue attunement tool to understand followership and political mobilisation, we are happy to discuss your intervention within your context. Please contact Evangelia Vergouli, evangelia.vergouli@open.ac.uk, Prof. Kesi Mahendran, kesi.mahendran@open.ac.uk, and Dr. Evangelos Ntontis, evangelos.ntontis@open.ac.uk.

[1] While great care was taken to produce videos that could serve as stimulus materials irrespective of national context, the films unavoidably showcase cultural and linguistic particularities pertaining to the UK. However, Evangelia found that both in pilot interviews and in her interview study with 20 Greek citizens (ages ranging between 21 and 78), participants fully engaged with the stimuli. This leads us to propose that the “Vote for me” films can be used with citizens in diverse national contexts, provided they are properly subtitled.

Appendix C: Sustaining Dialogue Attunement Tool

Introduction

This user guide develops the findings from the Four-country Pairing Study (Deliverable 6.4) into a Sustaining Dialogue Attunement Tool. This forms part of the set of Public Dialogue Attunement Tools provided by WP6 towards the political attunement toolkit led by WP7. The aim of the Sustaining Dialogue Attunement Tool is to offer those with political differences the space to develop a flexible understanding of those with whom they disagree and recognise their own capacity for sustaining dialogue. The tool consists of an oppositional thinking exercise in which a target group (see below) are paired together and are mediated to engage in political dialogue on a challenging issue (see Section A for an outline). Working with the tennis metaphor outlined in D6.5, the tool may offer both players the space to ‘use the entire court’ when engaging with one another (i.e.: they can agree, disagree, compromise, etc.). Here, the objective is not to ‘win the point’ (although that may be the aim for some), but, rather, to develop their ability to rally with each other to find out more about an oppositional view and their own democratic capacities.

Section A

Sustaining Dialogue Tool

The following section offers guidance to WP7 partners on how to use the sustaining dialogue tool to create a space for individuals to openly express their political views, respect differences, and recognise their capacity for sustaining dialogue.

Important: This is a significantly simplified version of the D6.4 study on which this is based. Therefore, it is advisable to read Section B and C of report 6.6 for an overview of the research and findings to contextualise the following intervention. Please feel free to contact Anthony, Anthony.english1@open.ac.uk, for further information regarding this tool.

Oppositional Thinking Exercise

This sustaining dialogue attunement tool aims to increase the target audience’s capacity for engaging in oppositional thinking by allowing them the training space to ‘practice’ such discussions.

Target Groups

While the final D6.4 report has three intended audiences, policymakers, dialogical researchers, and practitioners, the purpose of this guide is to align with the aims of WP 7. Therefore, this user guide focuses entirely on partners working in the field directly with participants (e.g.: a partner working with users of a service).

Example

Step 1 – Introducing the Political Issue

For the first task, the group are invited to view content (e.g.: news footage, YouTube, etc.) which depicts contrasting views on a contested political issue relevant to the location of the fieldwork. The aim is to understand the views they hold on to this issue in order to pair them together on potential differences between the individuals. For example, if the location were Pristina, the stimulus material could be directed towards the polarising issue of youth migration and the reasons why they are . For example, if the location were Pristina, the stimulus material could be directed towards the polarising issue of youth migration and the reasons why they are relocating to EU countries. News footage which depicts different views on this from those in Pristina offers the type of stimulus that evokes engagement (see basic primer infographic below as to the type of issues this raises). If the issue were immigration focused, D6.4’s material could also be used if in a relevant location (namely, Pristina, Malmo or the UK). Important to note, this first step must involve recording each group member’s views on the political issue in order to pair them together. To this end, a pro-forma, online content can be used (which I can create if needed) to allow them to express their views on the issue and why they believe what they do.

Step 2 – Pairing Participants Together

After a review of the completed pro-forma by the group facilitators, the group are divided into pairs. A third person can play the role of the mediator, whose role is to facilitate the discussions and maintaining the integrity of the task by not disclosing the questions or aims in advance. Ideally this would be one of the facilitating team but, if this is not possible, then other group members could be asked. The discussants will be paired together based on an opposing view (all of which is undisclosed to the pair). To continue with Kosovo’s ‘Brain drain’ example, one participant may argue that young people should have freedom of choice, whilst another may criticise them for being disloyal to the country. This difference would offer an ideal contrast worth exploring further as a paired discussion.

Step 3 – Paired Discussion: Developing a Connection

Based on findings from D6.4, the pairs’ discussions work ‘best’ (i.e.: they sustain dialogue to better understand one another despite disagreeing) if the initial discussion is based on views or life experiences shared by both participants. Therefore, in the first stage, the mediator’s role is to ask both participants to share some background information about themselves (education, family background) and their interests. Both are instructed to raise their hands whenever the other person identifies a connection (e.g.: same role in family – first-born, interest in politics, etc.).

Step 4 – Paired Discussion: Polarising Moment

After time spent exploring any shared connections, the mediator moves on to introducing the (potentially) polarising issue on which they disagree (based on the initial premise for pairing them together). It is important that the mediator does not highlight that they disagree but simply introduces the issue and asks the following questions in turn for each participant (only moving on to the next question for both after the answers have been fully explored). This allows the participants to discover that they disagree with one another as the discussion moves forward to avoid any negative priming.

1. What are your views on the issue of youth migration from Kosovo?
2. Why do you feel this way about the issue?
3. You seem to have different views about the issue - Why do you think this is?
4. What do you think the other person would benefit from knowing about this issue?

Clearly such discussions are a dynamic process in which the mediator may be required to offer additional prompts or steers based on the responses to explore their views further.

Step 5. Reflection

The final stage involves the group facilitators asking the trio to reflect together on the experience of discussing a (potentially) polarising political issue and then feedback to the rest of the group. Here are some suggested questions which could be asked for this group feedback session:

1. How did you find discussing this challenging political issue with others?
2. Were there any moments of disagreement between you and your partner – how did you find that? What did you do?
3. Do you feel you learnt anything about why someone may disagree with you on this issue?
4. For the mediators, how did you find this role? Did you learn anything about how we interact when discussing challenging political issues?

Outcomes

Self-report: The feedback session questions can be used to record qualitative feedback (create word clouds, etc) to assess how they engaged with the task and the potential for improvement.

Behavioural observations: During the exercise, the facilitators observe the interaction for each trio during both stages. It would also be valuable to assess the role the mediator plays in the discursive dynamic; both to consider the impact of this on the discussion and the efficacy of developing this exercise for future sessions with other target groups.

Section B

Four Country Sustaining Dialogue Overview

This guide draws from a post-doctoral study using a mixed-methods, quasi-experimental two study design which explored how individuals with contrasting views on the polarising issue of immigration could sustain dialogue when in direct conversation. In semi-structured interviews using country-relevant stimulus materials (contrasting map projections, footage of protests offering different views on immigration), Study A spoke with residents in four nations (Manchester - England, Pristina - Kosovo, Edinburgh - Scotland, and Malmö - Sweden) to understand their views about immigration. The interviews were analysed with a dialogical three-step analysis which was contextualised with data from a pre-interview questionnaire measuring immigration positivity, attitude certainty, and worldview endorsements. However, this step is not needed in order to use the sustained dialogue attunement tool.

Study B then paired residents from the same country together on two shared political positions they adopted in response to the same stimulus materials and a projected polarising issue between them.

Study B Pairings*	Shared Position One	Shared Position Two	Projected Polarising issue
Pairing A (Edinburgh): Gerado and Tyson	/-Green-Party-Member	/-Refugee-Advocate	Edinburgh community responses to refugees
Pairing B (Manchester): Kelsey and Bridget	/-Migration-Advocate	/-Social-Media-Critic	Democratic voting rights
Pairing C (Pristina): Flora and Arben	/-Border-Pragmatist	/-Migrating-Youth-Critic	Pristina community responses to refugees
Pairing D (Malmö): Amalia and Tobias	/-Threatened-Community-Advocate	'Acceptable Migrant' hierarchy (SR)	Socialism's potential to help migrants

*All names have been pseudomized.

The paired discussion structure involved asking them three questions on each of these two shared positions in the first stage. The participants were then introduced to a stimulus material highlighting a potentially polarising issue between them and asked questions which explored their views on the issue. The aim was to understand what factors allow individuals to navigate these challenging discussions and develop tools which could be implemented in real-world scenarios relevant to front-line practitioners. Important to note that the participants in Study B were unaware this was the intention of the research to maintain the integrity of the project.

Section C

Sustaining Dialogue Results (Study B)

Finally, here is a brief overview of the influencing factors and key strategies used by the pairs in Study B, which guided the development of the attunement tool.

1. Opinion Masking

The discursive move of advocating for another group to mask the person's own critical views of immigration was found in both studies (e.g.: an 'advocating-they' position - see extract 01). This is likely to be present when the person wishing to express this view is uncertain about how they will be received by others and is concerned with impression management (i.e.: wishes to avoid being perceived as prejudiced). Advocating for others that hold the view they wish to express offers a moderate way to navigate these two concerns.

Extract 01

Karli

And then you can be in other areas where all the, like, written text on the floor is different, you know? Even, like, all the stores, their facades. Like, when all the shops are in foreign script in a language that you can't even read, right? Not even, like, it's not in Swedish, it's not in English. It's in other languages, if you happen to live in an area where you become the minority, I can emphasise with them feeling unsafe or maybe they feel suddenly unsure about where they live (.) they think 'what is this place?'

2. Perceived Legitimacy and Attitude Certainty

Pairing C engaged in frequent disagreements during both stages of the discussion but were able to sustain dialogue despite this. An important influence here could be a perceived legitimacy both shared when discussing immigration and related issues. During the discussion on Sweden's immigration and refugee policies, both shared their life experiences as migrant parents and indicated to one another both were invested in the discussion. Furthermore, both self-reported a high level of certainty that their views on immigration were the correct ones to hold. This mutual respect for shared experiences and the confidence borne out of certainty could have been influencing factors in creating a discursive dynamic which allows them to engage with one another despite explicit differences.

3. Everyday Extremism Framing

During Pairing B's interaction, there was an example of a politically extreme idea being spread from one person to another via framing the issue as a 'fantasy-style' thought experiment. Specifically, that voting rights should be withdrawn for any member of the UK public who do not pass a test on democracy when voting (see extract 02). This fantasy framing seemed to encourage the other participant, after initially voicing reservations about the idea, to engage with the fantasy further on the benefits of limiting voting rights. This finding aligns with WP 4's findings on how memes with politically extreme content can spread effectively by framing the idea differently (be that through humour, a fantastical scenario, etc.) to diminish the explicit threat.

Extract 02

Kelsey

what I would like to see in my fantasy world is that alongside on that ballot paper are 10 questions which are an all-party they're constructed by all parties involved and I hate to say it even reform um UK and they have they have the questions and you have to answer the question by choosing the correct answer and if you get fewer than seven out of ten correct your vote doesn't count because if you're voting grossly misinformed then how could your vote have any validity as to what you are voting for so someone gets eight out of ten right and they're voting for Farage, I would count that vote but if they're only getting three out of ten correct and the voting for Rishi we throw out the vote people have to be informed about what they're voting for (...) yeah that's my fantasy! (laughs).

Bridget

I don't know, I don't (.) I don't think it would go down very well like with human rights (.) I don't know (.) No (...) I actually agree with it but like in my ideal I don't know (.) maybe I do (.) maybe I do completely agree but I feel bad because it makes sense to me (.) I completely agree with you Kelsey (.) it isn't like (.) it makes sense that people should there should be a bit of a verification of like 'do you know what's going on?' like 'do you know what this party believes in?' or 'what they're actually planning to do or have you read a few choice articles or a couple of Tik Tok videos?' like it does seem unfair that for people that really engage and really care and like whether it's right-wing or left-wing, like it doesn't really matter, but really engage what that party believes in and that aligns and then somebody's vote is like doesn't really (.) it's very it feels unfair sometimes, do you know?

4. Relevant Talking Points

The paired discussions highlighted the importance of relevant talking points for individuals to engage completely in the process. The seemingly irrelevant or unrepresentative use of content as stimulus materials for Pairing C provided the opportunity for a participant to critique the facilitator's questions and distance themselves from the discussion during a moment of disagreement to stop the dialogue.

Please attribute the Sustaining Dialogue Attunement Tool accredited to lead research Anthony English as follows: English, A., Mahendran, K, and Obradović, S. (D6.4). Sustaining Dialogue Attunement Tool, Horizon-Europe. Available on COR-DIS.

References

The following references are not essential reading but are intended to offer a broader context for understanding the intentions of this deliverable.

- English, A., and Mahendran, K. (2021) Sustaining Dialogue in Polarised Political Contexts: Moving beyond Shared-Identity to Dialogical Position Exchanges. *International Review of Theoretical Psychologies*. 2 (1).
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- Mahendran, K., English, A., and Nieland, S. (2020) Populism vs. the People: How citizen's social representations of home destabilize national populism's territorial vision. *Journal of Theoretical Social Psychology*, <https://doi.org/10.1002/jts5.82>

Appendix D: BBC Films & Open Access Self-Coaching Attunement Interactives

1. BBC Film - How quickly can online hate spread? (7.00min)
2. Do Your Relationships Need an Everyday Extremism Check? Online self-test interactive.
3. Are you an Online Detective? Online self-test interactive
4. BBC Film - Why are we obsessed with being armchair detectives?
5. i-Attune – online self-test interactive.

<https://connect.open.ac.uk/society-psychology-and-criminology/morning-live/> - all films and interactives are available here, except for i-Attune which will be available by 20th June.

